

AMIGDALA

**Alliance for Modelling Industries towards the
Green Deal's objectives And circuLArity**

**D5.2 – Dissemination, exploitation, and
communication (DEC) – Reporting Period 1**

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF FIGURES	5
LIST OF TABLES	6
1. AMIGDALA Project Summary	7
2. Executive summary	7
3. Acronyms and abbreviations	9
4. Introduction	10
5. Objectives of the C&D Plan	11
6. Targeted Audiences and Key Messages	11
7. Tools, Channels and Key Performance Indicators KPIs	14
8. Community of Practice (COP)	30
9. Levels of dissemination	31
10. Methodology	32
11. Timeline	33
12. Actions M1-M6	34
13. Conclusion	53
14. Annex: Dissemination Tables	53

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: AMIGDALA Poster.....	21
Figure 2: AMIGDALA Factsheet	22
Figure 3: AMIGDALA Roll Up.....	23
Figure 4: AMIGDALA Brochure	24
Figure 5: AMIGDALA project presentation.	24
Figure 6: AMIGDALA LinkedIn, YouTube and X Accounts.....	26
Figure 7: AMIGDALA Logo Options and Final Choice.....	27
Figure 8: AMIGDALA's Brand Guidelines	28
Figure 9: AMIGDALA Workshops Section.....	34
Figure 10: AMIGDALA's banner of its first workshop.	35
Figure 11: Banner of the second workshop	36
Figure 12: PROCESSES 4 PLANET publication about the AMIGDALA first webinar.....	37
Figure 13: PROCESSES 4 PLANET LinkedIn Post about the AMIGDALA second webinar.....	37
Figure 14: AMIGDALA's Website Analytics	39
Figure 15: AMIGDALA's Home Page.....	40
Figure 16: AMIGDALA's Newsletter.....	42
Figure 17: AMIGDALA's First Press Release.....	43
Figure 18: AMIGDALA featured in the A.Spire Website.....	44
Figure 19: AMIGDALA featured on the WIT News website.....	44
19 Figure 20: X (Twitter) Analytics M1-M6.....	45
20 Figure 21: LinkedIn Analytics M1-M6	46
Figure 22: YouTube Analytics M1-M6	46
Figure 23: AMIGDALA's Related Initiatives Tab	47
Figure 24: AMIGDALA's Roll Up at INDtech 2024	48
Figure 25: AMIGDALA's PPT Template.	49
Figure 26: AMIGDALA Website Dissemination Materials.....	49
Figure 27: AMIGDALA's CoP Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)	50
Figure 28: AMIGDALA's website, CoP webinars tab.....	51
Figure 29: AMIGDALA's CoP Registration Tab.....	52
Figure 30: AMIGDALA's Social Media Post COP.....	52

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Target audiences.	12
Table 2: AMIGDALA's Key Messages.....	13
Table 3: AMIGDALA's List of KPIs	15
Table 4: Page content-structure of the AMIGDALA project website.....	18

1. AMIGDALA Project Summary

Transitioning industries towards climate neutrality by 2050, as directed by the European Green Deal, presents a multi-faceted challenge. Sustainable industry for Europe must become climate-neutral, while it also remaining globally competitive and resilient. Changing course requires foresight to oversee the complex interplay between demand, global trade and industrial production. Decision-makers will choose from options available to them, to make policy, regulate or invest in the deployment of novel technologies in public infrastructure and industrial assets.

The objective of the EU-funded AMIGDALA project is to deliver policy scenarios and projections of industrial development based on indicators and control options that decision-makers recognize.

For the projections, an integrated modelling tool will be developed that links demand & trade, industrial production, primary generation of energy & feedstock and climate effects, spanning the period 1990 to 2070. Modelling of local decision-making will zoom into the options and choices made by industry clusters and the utility operators that provide them with resources.

2. Executive summary

This document provides a comprehensive description of the first Dissemination and Communication (D&C) plan for the AMIGDALA Project. It will outline the project's target audiences, key messages, communication channels, and roles and responsibilities. Project branding elements, including the logo, templates, social media profiles, and website. This plan will be continuously monitored and updated throughout the project's lifecycle to ensure its communication efforts remain adaptable and impactful.

The D&C plan will be delivered in three stages.

This initial plan (D5.2), delivered in Month 6 (M6), establishes the foundation by outlining the project's target audiences, key messages, communication channels, and partner roles and responsibilities. The project branding elements, including logos, templates, social media profiles, and the project website, was finalized by Month 3 (M3) as described in the following sections. Subsequent updates will build upon this initial plan. The second update (D5.3), delivered in Month 18 (M18), will monitor and assess the effectiveness of the communication efforts implemented in the first half of the project. The third update (D6.1) in Month 36 will include the updates on collaboration activities.

Finally, the last update (D7.1), will be delivered in Month 48 (M48), will provide a comprehensive review of the communication activities undertaken throughout the project's duration.

2.1 Context of WP5-7: Dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) – Reporting Period 1/2/3

The main goal of the work package 5 (WP5), Dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) – Reporting Period 1, is to coordinate the efforts of the consortium between month 1 and month 18 to actively involve the project's stakeholders in the open R&D cycle of the project, from the design phase to the outputs' review, validation and uptake, and maximise the impact by adequately conveying the project's messages and results to targeted audiences and preparing IP and exploitation measures for the results. The following work package (WP6) covers the second period, from month 19 (M19) to month 36 (M36), of the project's Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication activities, continuing the work of WP5. This subsequent work package (WP7) ensures the continuity and progression of DEC activities into the project's third period, building on the foundations laid by WP5.

2.2 Objectives of Tasks 5.2, 6.1, 7.1 – D&C Activities

The aim of this task is to prepare and execute the project's dissemination and communication plan. SIE will coordinate the work, preparing the different deliveries of the D&C plan (D5.2 in M6, D5.3 in M18, D6.1 in M36 and D7.1 in M48) and updating the different activities performed by partners.

This first D&C plan by M6 outlines the project's audiences, key messages, and channels for the communication and the dissemination, including roles and responsibilities. The project branding (logo, templates, etc.), social media profiles and website were ready in M3 (Milestone 13). The task 6.1 will continue the work of T5.2, implementing the DEC activities during the 2nd reporting period of the project. The activities will be monitored and reviewed in the M36 update (D6.1).

Finally, the 7.1 task will continue the work of T6.1, implementing the dissemination and communication activities during the last reporting period of the project. The activities will be monitored and reviewed in the M48 update (D7.1).

3. Acronyms and abbreviations

COP	Community of Practice
D&C PLAN	Dissemination and Communication
D-FRAMEWORK	Decision-framework
DOA	Description of action
EC	European Commission
ECEMF	European Climate + Energy Modelling Forum
GA4	Google Analytics 4
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GP	General Public
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OPEN ENT	open ENERGY TRansition ANalyses for a low-Carbon Economy
PM	Policy Makers
P4PLANET	Processes4Planet
R&D	Research and Development
SC	Scientific Community
SIE	Sustainable Innovations Europe
SI	Software industry
TM	Trade Media
WP	Work Package

4. Introduction

This comprehensive document outlines the AMIGDALA project's D&C plan, a multifaceted strategy to effectively engage target audiences and amplify the project's impactful research and development.

The plan dives into several crucial aspects for successful dissemination. We will # identify specific target groups to tailor communication approaches, craft compelling messages for all channels, and define the optimal platforms to reach them.

This includes the project website, social media, printed materials, newsletters, press releases, events, and project videos. Establishing a strong visual identity with logos and branding will solidify the project's image.

Compliance with EU funding requirements will be ensured through the inclusion of necessary disclaimers. A detailed social media strategy will guide our efforts to connect with audiences and build communities around the project.

Strategies for creating and distributing informative printed materials and regular newsletters will keep stakeholders engaged.

Generating media interest through press releases and strategic event participation will raise project visibility. Engaging project videos will showcase the AMIGDALA project's goals and progress. This document will define different levels of dissemination based on audiences and information sensitivity and provide a clear understanding of the methodology used for disseminating project information.

Finally, the plan will offer a focused overview of communication and dissemination activities undertaken in the last six months to provide context for the upcoming plan. By meticulously addressing these critical components, this D&C plan aims to ensure impactful knowledge sharing and project visibility throughout the AMIGDALA project's lifecycle.

5. Objectives of the C&D Plan

The AMIGDALA project's C&D Plan focuses on maximizing the reach and impact of its research findings. The plan prioritizes targeted dissemination by identifying specific audiences who will benefit most. This includes researchers, industry stakeholders, and policymakers. By understanding their needs, the C&D Plan tailors communication strategies for each group, ensuring clear and impactful messaging resonates with them.

The plan acknowledges the importance of selecting the right communication channels. This may include a project website, targeted social media channels, press releases for wider announcements, conferences and workshops for direct interaction, and exploring other relevant channels based on the audience and project goals.

Finally, the C&D Plan recognizes the value of collaboration within the project team. By clearly defining the roles and responsibilities of each partner regarding communication activities, the plan ensures a coordinated effort that maximizes outreach potential.

6. Targeted Audiences and Key Messages

6.1 Target Audiences

AMIGDALA has initially identified several stakeholder groups who would find the project's results valuable. These groups will be targeted by the project's Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) activities. The project has categorized these audiences into two groups: primary target audiences (those who will directly use the project's solutions) and secondary audiences (other interested parties).

Stakeholders are individuals or groups with a vested interest in the success and outcomes of a project. They are crucial for the AMIGDALA project as their engagement, feedback, and support are essential for achieving the project's objectives.

This subsection identifies and categorizes the primary and secondary stakeholders who will benefit from AMIGDALA. These include European, national, and regional policymakers, sectoral associations, industry stakeholders, investors, financial institutions, and the public.

By tailoring communication efforts to meet the needs and interests of these diverse groups, the project aims to foster broad engagement, support informed decision-making, and promote the adoption of sustainable and climate-neutral practices in line with the European Green Deal's objectives. More information can be found on the deliverable D5.1 Stakeholder Engagement Plan and in the D5.7 Project website.

Table 1: Target audiences.

Target Audience	Description	Impacts
Policymakers	European, national, and regional authorities responsible for designing and enforcing policies on energy, materials, industry, climate, and environment.	Science-based policymaking; assessment of policy impacts; setting and exploring policy targets; enhancing policy effectiveness.
Sectoral Associations	European and national associations representing energy-intensive industries, such as chemicals, cement, steel, aluminium, glass, and mining.	Evidence-based support for policies; identifying opportunities; preparing for future trends; enhancing credibility and influence.
Industry Stakeholders	Companies in energy-intensive industries, clean power generation, industrial manufacturing, and construction.	Access to sustainable materials and products; opportunities for decarbonization; cost savings; increased competitiveness.
Investors and Finance Sector	Investors in clean power generation and industrial manufacturing; banks and financial institutions.	Informed investment decisions; development of financing models for climate-neutral and circular solutions.
Public-Private Partnerships	Partnerships such as Processes4Planet (P4P), focusing on transforming European process industries.	Support for operational objectives, such as efficient CO ₂ valorization, circularity hubs, and market frameworks for climate-neutral solutions.
Industry Cluster Organizations	Organizations supporting member companies in implementing climate-neutral solutions.	Assistance in achieving EU climate targets; support for decarbonization initiatives; fostering collaboration and innovation.
Research and Academia	Applied research institutes, national laboratories, and universities.	Access to the latest knowledge and tools for developing new technologies; opportunities for collaboration and research advancements.
General Public	The broader community affected by industrial practices and environmental policies.	Overall reduction of emissions; improved sustainability of products and services; enhanced quality of life.

6.2 Key Messages

The success of the AMIGDALA project depends crucially on effective communication and engagement with a diverse range of stakeholders. Identifying and understanding these target audiences is crucial for tailoring D&C strategies to ensure maximum impact and uptake of project outcomes.

The following table shows the target groups identified within the AMIGDALA project and a brief description of each stakeholder group.

Table 2: AMIGDALA's Key Messages

Work Packages	Key Messages	Target Groups
D-framework and integrated model architecture design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishes the foundation for the AMIGDALA project model. Defines the framework for data integration and analysis. 	<p>Policymakers, Research and Academia</p>
Model development & PoC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develops core functionalities of the AMIGDALA model. Tests and validates the model's capabilities through Proof-of-Concept activities. 	<p>Policymakers, Industry Stakeholders, Research and Academia</p>
Technical completion of the integrated model and the stakeholder dashboard	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Finalizes the development of the AMIGDALA model. Creates a user-friendly dashboard for stakeholder interaction. 	<p>Policymakers, Sectoral Associations, Industry Stakeholders, Public-Private Partnerships, Industry Cluster Organizations</p>
Deploy the integrated model to evaluate pathways towards climate neutrality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilizes the AMIGDALA model to simulate different scenarios for achieving climate neutrality. Provides insights into the effectiveness of various policy and industry actions. 	<p>Policymakers, Sectoral Associations, Industry Stakeholders, Public-Private Partnerships, Industry Cluster Organizations</p>
Dissemination, exploitation and communication - Reporting Period 1, 2, 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lays the groundwork for project communication and outreach strategies. Establishes a stakeholder management plan. Refines and implements communication strategies to reach target audiences. Develops further plans for project exploitation and intellectual property rights. Maintains ongoing communication efforts throughout the project. Identifies opportunities for project exploitation and IPR management. 	<p>All Target Groups</p>

7. Tools, Channels and Key Performance Indicators KPIs

To ensure effective communication and maximize the project's impact, AMIGDALA will utilize a strategic online tools (such as the website, newsletters or social media), channels, and KPIs. This section outlines the framework for measuring the success of the Communication and Dissemination Plan.

KPIs serve as quantifiable metrics that enable the project consortium to assess progress, measure success, and identify areas for improvement in communication and dissemination activities.

By setting clear and measurable KPIs aligned with the objectives outlined in the C&D Plan, the project can track various aspects of its communication efforts, including reach, engagement, and impact. This data-driven approach not only facilitates informed decision-making but also enables timely adjustments to strategies and tactics to optimize outcomes. Additionally, well-defined KPIs provide a basis for accountability and transparency, allowing stakeholders to evaluate the project's performance against predefined benchmarks. Ultimately, the establishment of KPIs ensures that the C&D Plan remains a dynamic and responsive framework, capable of driving meaningful results and maximizing the project's overall impact and effectiveness.

The goal is to deliver easily understandable information to different audiences about the project's objectives and outcomes. Leveraging the communication channels of AMIGDALA ensures that critical insights and developments are effectively disseminated to all stakeholders. This enhances engagement, supports informed decision-making, and promotes transparency, ultimately driving the successful adoption of sustainable and climate-neutral practices.

The following list describes de KPIs of the project:

Table 3: AMIGDALA's List of KPIs

Tool/ Channel	Target Group	KPI
Scientific Publications	Academia, research teams in industries	+4 papers submitted
White Papers	Industry stakeholders	One per subsector +6 total
Scientific Workshops	Academia, research teams in industries	+3 workshops, targeting 25 attendees each. Final workshop +100 attendees
Industry Roundtables	Industries, investors	+6 roundtables
Conferences and Events Attended	All	+20 events attended
Project Website & Social Media	All	Website: 600-1,200 visits/year Social media: >100 followers, >2% engagement rate
Press Releases	Media	100 media outlets/articles covered
Newsletters	Academia, industry	2 per year >100 subscribers >15% opening rate
Videos	All	2 videos +300 views on YouTube
Printed Materials	All	+300 printed brochures

7.1 Scientific Publications

The inclusion of scientific publications constitutes a vital component of the AMIGDALA project. These publications serve as the primary mechanism for disseminating the project's findings, advancements, and research outcomes to the global academic and scientific community.

AMIGDALA's Project partners are expected to submit at least 4 peer-reviewed scientific papers by the end of the project, ensuring Open Access. Some of the journals identified include [Open Research Europe](#), [International Journal of Production Economics](#), [Technological Forecasting and Social Change](#), or [Journal of Cleaner Production](#). After the project, effects will still be measured according to citation-based metrics such as citation counts.

The publication along the project will be encouraged, so peer reviewed feedback on the papers submitted contributes to the Open Innovation strategy of the project.

7.2 White Papers

Once the AMIGDALA project yields specific and robust results for sectoral transition pathways and scenarios, short white papers will be produced with the support of SIE for the graphical format. The purpose of these white papers is to provide easily understandable documents containing key insights for industry stakeholders in the European industrial sub-sectors. One white paper will be produced for each subsector, resulting in a total of six or more.

7.3 Scientific Workshops

As described in the KPIs section of AMIGDALA, scientific workshops will be held for academic peers and industry research teams. These early presentations aim to gather feedback and share initial findings in a smaller, discussion-oriented setting (around 25 attendees). A final project workshop will be organised to present the main results and outcomes of the project, targeting +100 attendees. The format will be, preliminarily, online. Cooperation with allied projects and initiatives will be sought.

Focused discussions called roundtables will be conducted with industry representatives, including investors. These discussions will help the project understand their specific needs and tailor research and development efforts accordingly. Sectoral workshops will delve deeper into specific industry requirements, and white paper presentations will directly disseminate project findings.

Project partners will actively participate in relevant conferences, workshops, and sector-related events across national, European, and international levels. This participation allows them to connect with a wider audience from academia, industry, investors, and policymakers, raising awareness about the project's goals and outcomes.

SIE will provide logistical support for all events. TNO, the project coordinator, will offer general guidance. Initially, all these events (workshops, roundtables, conferences) will be held online, with the possibility of transitioning to in-person formats depending on future developments.

7.4 Industry roundtables

In the same line of the scientific workshops, the purpose here is to receive the specific feedback of industry stakeholders, to better direct the R&D work to serve their needs and interests. Sectoral industry workshops will be organised to gather their needs and expectations, making them match the presentation of the sectoral white papers as a means of direct dissemination. Six or more will be produced.

7.5 Conferences and Events Attended

To meet target audiences, project partners will attend sector-related events, conferences, and workshops. They will also spread the word about the project's goals and outcomes. Access to target audiences at the national, European, and worldwide levels will be made possible by these events. Different events will be attended, shifting from the ones focused on academic work, to industry and investors, and policymakers.

7.6 Project Website

SIE as the communication and dissemination work package leader, registered this URL name at the very beginning of the project. Since all the promotion, communication and dissemination will be centred around the brand name “AMIGDALA PROJECT”, it was crucial to secure this easy-to-find URL. The .eu domain was chosen to emphasize the European perspective of the project.

The AMIGDALA Website will be the primary source of information for external parties, providing updates on project activities and achievements to all target audiences. The website aims to inform the community and associated industries about project developments, but also to present the project's achievements and novel pilot lines to the public.

All partners will contribute to the website by providing relevant project information. All communication efforts by project partners and social media will always be redirected to the AMIGDALA website. Traffic to the website will be increased by creating mutual links between the

partners' websites and other relevant websites and social media channels. It will include at least one video (embedded from [YouTube](#)) to introduce the main project ambition.

The table below, an overview of the different pages with a short description and the hyperlink is provided:

Table 4: Page content-structure of the AMIGDALA project website.

Page	Description
Home	The home contains information about the project concept, specific objectives; and the latest project news.
About Project	The About Project tab is designed to give a more comprehensive view of the project methodology through the description of the project concept, the current challenges with the EU Green Deal, its impacts, and methodology.
About Partners	This page contains information about each of the AMIGDALA consortium partners and their main expertise.
Related initiatives	This section is part of the clustering strategy where SIE added related initiatives such as INITIATE, GREENSTEEL and OPEN ENTRANCE.
Documents	In this section, all the public project information will be uploaded. At this moment (M6), all the dissemination materials have been shared: Press release, brochure, factsheet, poster, roll up, project presentation, and logo.
Community of Practice	In cooperation with Deloitte, SIE created this tab to explain and encourage the audience to subscribe to the CoP. An explanation, some practical information and a FAQ section were included.
Webinars	An informative section about the upcoming webinars and the recording of previous ones was included to store and share the different activities conducted within the CoP.
CoP Registration	A dedicated space was created to invite the different stakeholders to be part of the AMIGDALA community of practice. This page includes a form where users can sign in.
News	The news section is expected to be updated at least one time per month sharing information to engage with the different stakeholders. Some content examples can include partner interviews, events where the project has been showcased, milestones, etc.
Contact	On this page, users can send an email to the project partners. SIE will lead the email account and will share the emails with the corresponding responsible.
Privacy Policy	This section contains information concerning the GDPR EU regulation and how the data is protected and processed.

Cookies Policy	This section contains information about the cookies. The definition of the cookies, the type of cookies, and the elimination process are included.
Legal Notices	Last but not least, the legal notice refers to the general conditions that regulate the use and access to the Internet service for the project website.

The website will be maintained for the project duration and an additional two years after completion. Afterwards, SIE will erase all collected data unless legal obligations require longer storage.

Statistical data will be collected about the website visitors that subsequently will be analysed by Google Analytics software and included in the project reports. The website will be responsive to work on a variety of devices and screen sizes, such as smartphones.

SIE uses Google Analytics to analyze anonymized website traffic data. This data is included in project reports to understand user engagement. You can learn more about Google Analytics privacy practices [here](#).

More information about the project website, see deliverable "D5.7 Project Website." This deliverable contains the project's information (goals, work plan, partners, contact forms, etc.)

7.7 Newsletters and press releases

Digital newsletters will be prepared and distributed every 6 months. This newsletter may include project updates, announcements, interviews with partners, and other relevant information for stakeholders and subscribers. It will be distributed via MailChimp, posted on the AMIGDALA project website for easy access and on social media.

To maximize reach and engagement, project updates may also be featured in the respective digital newsletters of our partners. These partner newsletters are distributed directly to their industry-specific contact lists, further amplifying project visibility and impact.

Press releases will be published to announce newsworthy developments during the project. They will be written in English and sent to the European press and national journalists, with the help of the project partners. Partners are encouraged to translate into their local languages and send them to maximise the impact of the project.

7.8 Project Videos

The project plans to produce at least 2 project videos will be generated. The first one, by the beginning of the project, conveying the main

project objectives and impacts in a language easy to understand by non-expert audiences. The second one, by the end of the project, wrapping up the main project results and successes. SIE will develop the storyboard and after approval of all partners.

7.9 Printed Materials

SIE has created a comprehensive suite of communication materials to empower partner outreach and event participation. A [poster](#), a [factsheet](#), a [roll-up](#), a [project presentation](#) and a [brochure](#) all designed for distribution to partner networks and use at conferences, exhibitions, and other relevant events.

These materials are valuable tools for sharing project objectives, achievements, and impacts with various stakeholders, including partners, policymakers, industry professionals, and the public. By providing complete information in different formats such as brochures, posters, and presentations, the project can improve visibility, build awareness, and foster engagement, ultimately facilitating collaboration and maximizing the project's overall impact.

Figure 1: AMIGDALA Poster

AMIGDALA

GD

WHAT IS AMIGDALA?

AMIGDALA is a Horizon Europe project which seeks to facilitate decision-makers in governments and industry to define and evaluate pathways and market uptakes of transformative solutions for circular, climate neutral and competitive industries.

AMIGDALA

Modelling Industries towards the Green Deal

OBJECTIVES

- Developing an integrated modelling approach for the EU's energy intensive sectors.
- Addressing the lack of standardisation in model integration.
- Providing consistent and validated data to support climate objectives.
- Enhancing transparency and understanding between model results and decision-makers' needs.
- Driving informed decisions towards a sustainable and carbon-neutral future.

PROJECT PARTNERS

KU LEUVEN **sitech** **GreenDecision**

International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis **Bfi** **ENEA**

Deloitte **DECHEMA** **TNO**

Sustainable INNOVATIONS **vito**

www.amigdalaproject.eu

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Figure 2: AMIGDALA Factsheet

AMIGDALA

Figure 3: AMIGDALA Roll Up

AMIGDALA

PROJECT PARTNERS

International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), BpI, TNO, DEHEMA, vito, sitech SERVICES, ENEA, KU LEUVEN, GreenDecision, Sustainable INNOVATIONS, Deloitte, europeanresearchservices

DESCRIPTION

AMIGDALA is a Horizon Europe project which seeks to facilitate decision-makers in governments and industry to define and evaluate pathways and market updates of transformative solutions for circular, climate and competitive industries.

OBJECTIVES

The overall objective of AMIGDALA is to assist government and industry decision-makers in defining and evaluating pathways towards circular, climate-neutral, and competitive industries, using common databases and integrated models aligned with the Green Deal's sustainability objectives by:

- Developing an integrated modelling approach for the EU's energy-intensive sector.
- Addressing the lack of standardisation in model integration.
- Providing consistent and validated data to support climate objectives.
- Enhancing transparency and understanding between model results and decision makers' needs.
- Driving informed decisions towards a sustainable and carbon-neutral future.

METHODOLOGY

Project Management and Coordination

	WPS1	WPS2	WPS3	WPS4
Design	Design of the WPS	Technical description WPS	Development WPS	
Modeling	Modeling of demand, industrial production, trade and climate impact	Modeling of demand, industrial production, trade and climate impact	Modeling of demand, industrial production, trade and climate impact	Modeling of demand, industrial production, trade and climate impact
Validation	Validation of model results			
Dissemination	Dissemination of results	Dissemination of results	Dissemination of results	Dissemination of results

IMPACTS

- Strategic Alignment:** AMIGDALA will ensure that decisions are in line with the sustainability goals of the European Green Deal, promoting harmony with broader environmental objectives.
- Industry Transformation:** The initiative will guide industries toward sustainable practices, contributing significantly to both environmental and economic progress by steering them strategically.
- Informed Decision-Making:** AMIGDALA will provide decision-makers with comprehensive insights, empowering them to make strategic choices that align with climate neutrality and sustainability goals.
- Impact Analysis:** The project will assess the consequences of governmental and industrial decisions, shedding light on their effects on emissions, energy demand, and material usage.

Figure 4: AMIGDALA Brochure

1. AMIGDALA
Modelling industries towards the Green Deal

2. ABOUT the AMIGDALA project
AMIGDALA provides decision-makers on policy and investments with perspectives on the deployment of transformative solutions to make industrial production in Europe climate neutral and competitive.

3. OBJECTIVES
AMIGDALA provides decision-makers on policy and investments with perspectives on the deployment of transformative solutions to make industrial production in Europe climate neutral and competitive.

4. APPROACH
The AMIGDALA model will present results in actionable terms to users. This way we close the gap between abstract results and actual decisions.

5. OUTCOMES & IMPACTS
Outcomes:
• Transparent and verifiable pathways of change towards the Green Deal objectives
• Scenarios of public and private decisions to access the pathways
• Conditions for transformative solutions to become investable and be deployed by industry
• Knowledge about climate neutral and competitive production understood by academia and industry

6. IMPLEMENTATION
Project Management and Coordination

7. CONSORTIUM
Suppliers: Decision analytics & user interaction, Energy and process technology, Scenario & modeling, Dissemination, exploitation, and communication, Project management
Partner: BpI, DEHEMA, ENEA, IIASA, KU Leuven, Sustainable Innovations, TNO, vito, sitech SERVICES

8. AMIGDALA
WWW.AMIGDALA.PROJECT.EU
AMIGDALA PROJECT
AMIGDALA PROJECT
info@amigdalaproject.eu

Figure 5: AMIGDALA project presentation.

7.10 Social Media

According to the [European Research Executive Agency](#), Social media is an effective and engaging tool that allows you to instantly communicate to your audiences at a low-cost.

The project has social media presence on X (formerly known as Twitter) and LinkedIn to ensure wider dissemination to different age groups and target audiences. These platforms will be used to not only announce project developments but, more importantly, drive traffic to the project website.

The AMIGDALA project recognizes the power of social media for reaching diverse audiences and maximizing project impact. To achieve this, the project utilizes platforms like [X] (formerly Twitter) and LinkedIn.

Beyond simply announcing project developments, AMIGDALA leverages social media to cultivate a community of interest. Since Project Month 1 (M1), consistent content has been posted, raising awareness about the project's scope and upcoming presentations. This initial phase focuses on building a strong foundation, creating a ready audience for future project results.

Social media plays a key role in driving traffic to the project website. However, effective communication goes beyond simply pushing out messages. SIE will be actively monitoring social media analytics. This allows for a deeper understanding of the audience demographics (including age groups), content performance, and user engagement with project messages (including individuals and organizations who promote the project). Based on these insights, communication efforts will be continuously optimized for maximum reach and impact.

Consortium partners are encouraged to actively engage with the project's social media channels by following, liking, commenting, and sharing posts. Additionally, partners are encouraged to share project updates on their own communication channels, such as websites and social media networks. To support this partner engagement, SIE will provide guidance and assistance on best practices for maximizing their impact.

By implementing this multifaceted social media strategy, AMIGDALA fosters a vibrant online community, optimizes communication for maximum reach, and leverages partnerships to ensure the project's information reaches a broad and diverse audience.

Figure 6: AMIGDALA LinkedIn, YouTube and X Accounts

7.11 Project Identity

The establishment of a project identity is crucial for effective D&C plan of project goals, activities, and achievements. This identity serves as a visual representation of the project's core values and objectives. This section details the development process of the AMIGDALA project's visual identity, encompassing the selection of a logo, the creation of brand guidelines, and the integration of required disclaimers.

7.11.1 Project logo

AMIGDALA's visual identity started in the first month (M1) of the project. SIE led the process by presenting three logo options to all partner organizations. Partners actively participated in a democratic voting process to select the final logo. The logo features a stylized combination of the letter's "G" and "D" in a modern, interconnected design. Using a gradient color scheme transitioning from green to blue to purple, giving it a dynamic and contemporary look. Below the graphic element, the word "AMIGDALA" is written in a clean, sans-serif font, which is modern and easy to read. This ensured that the chosen design reflected the project's shared goals and resonated with AMIGDALA's overall vision.

AMIGDALA

Figure 7: AMIGDALA Logo Options and Final Choice

7.11.2 Brand guidelines and templates

Recognizing the importance of a strong brand identity for successful project, AMIGDALA prioritized creating a distinct and cohesive visual language from the outset. This commitment materialized in the form of brand guidelines (see figure 2). These guidelines define a logo, a harmonious color palette, specific typography choices, and a set of visuals. All these elements reflect the project's core principles and objectives. By ensuring a consistent presentation across all communication channels, both online and offline, this strong brand identity and emphasizes the memorability of the project.

Figure 8: AMIGDALA's Brand Guidelines

7.11.3 Disclaimers

According to Article 17 (Communication, dissemination, and visibility) of the Grant Agreement, the AMIGDALA project's beneficiaries have already considered the legal obligations regarding communication, dissemination, and visibility activities.

This includes providing targeted information about the project and its results to multiple audiences in a strategic, coherent, and effective manner. Before engaging in any communication or dissemination activity with significant media impact, beneficiaries informed the granting authority.

Moreover, all D&C activities related to the project, such as media relations, conferences, seminars, and information materials, have already acknowledged the support of the European Union and displayed the European flag emblem and funding statement. The European flag emblem has been displayed distinctively and separately, without modification, and no other visual identity or logo has been used to highlight EU support. When displayed alongside other logos, the European emblem has been equally prominent. The European emblem was extracted from [the official EU website](#).

Beneficiaries have utilized the European emblem for their obligations under this article without prior approval, in accordance with the grant agreement. However, it is noted that this does not grant them exclusive use rights. Additionally, they have refrained from appropriating the emblem or any similar trademark or logo. All communication and dissemination activities have used factually accurate information to maintain the quality of information provided.

To fulfil these obligations, a disclaimer has been included in all communication materials, stating, ***Funded by the European Union under the grant agreement 101138534. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.***

In addition to the EU disclaimer, the website also features the logo of Processes4Planet, a European co-programmed public-private partnership established between [A.SPIRE](#) (the private entity) and the European Commission within the framework of Cluster 4 (Digital, Industry and Space) of the Horizon Europe funding program. This logo will be included in specific communications. [Process4Planet](#) is a European co-programmed public-private partnership established between A.SPIRE, as the private entity, and the European Commission in the context of Cluster 4 (Digital, Industry and Space) of the Horizon Europe funding programme.

8 Community of Practice (COP)

As part of the AMIGDALA project, the Community of Practice (COP) will be established, bringing together a diverse group of key stakeholders, including industry associations, policymakers, and companies. This collaborative and voluntary group will play a crucial role in providing feedback and guidance throughout the project's duration. This COP will ensure that the AMIGDALA model meets stakeholder needs and expectations.

By actively engaging with these stakeholders, the COP aims to ensure that the AMIGDALA model is not only practical but also meets the specific needs of decision-makers. Their input will be instrumental in shaping the format and content of the project's final outcomes. This page serves as a comprehensive resource, offering clear explanations about the goals and ambitions of the Community of Practice.

It details the various stakeholder categories involved, highlights the benefits of being part of the community, and provides practical information for potential members.

Instructions for joining the COP, staying connected, and accessing the Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs) are all included to facilitate seamless participation and engagement. By fostering an inclusive and well-informed COP, the AMIGDALA project aims to create an impactful model that is grounded in real-world insights and expertise.

9 Levels of dissemination

This section explores the various levels of dissemination, noting that key target groups operate at different geographic scales. This variation influences the choice of communication tools and media, ensuring strategies are tailored to effectively reach and engage each audience segment

9.1 National Level

To ensure effective communication across Europe, the project will establish a national dissemination strategy for each partner country. This collaborative approach will involve sharing best practices for national outreach, co-organizing national events (workshops, conferences) to share project results, and contributing content to each other's D&C materials.

9.2 European Level

The European Commission will be informed about the results via the periodic reporting of the project (mid-term review, minutes of periodical meetings, updates of this document) to modify related regulations if necessary and to propose collaboration with other ongoing projects on dissemination activities.

9.3 Worldwide Level

The results will be communicated to relevant international organisations, so scientific findings can be transformed into practical information, regulations, and guidelines. Electronic resources will be disseminated via direct mail to designated organisations and stakeholders to enhance public awareness. To facilitate knowledge transfer at both research and industrial levels, technical journals, conferences, workshops at national and international levels, industry meetings, and participation in industrial forums will be used.

10 Methodology

The following internal and external D&C activities will be undertaken during the project's lifetime and afterward to ensure that the results of AMIGDALA project are efficiently and effectively communicated to the project partners, stakeholders, and broader audiences.

10.11 Internal communication

Effective internal communication is key to sharing information and ensuring that the deliverables are met. Therefore, annual face-to-face meetings and conference calls will take place to exchange project information, update progress, and share results. Consortium and technical meetings will take place at least one time a year, while Microsoft Teams and/or teleconferencing services will be used to facilitate collaboration within WPs.

Apart from specific emails, taking advantage of the at least one yearly general assembly, SIE will ask partners for their support on the upcoming dissemination and communication activities and events to update the Communication & Dissemination Plan and streamline a content curation process. This will allow the partners to take a more focused and systematic approach, strengthening actions taken to communicate and report on the project. A delegate from all consortium partners of AMIGDALA will attend this meeting.

10.12 External communication

Every effort will be made to publicize the work of the consortium via the media, publications, conference presentations, trade fairs, and workshops, as well as through the Commission and industry bodies. Results of the project will be disseminated via reports, scientific papers, and technical articles. All public communication, and in particular scientific publications, will be made open access, to facilitate scientific exchange.

All project partners are expected to support dissemination, to ensure that stakeholders will be engaged throughout the lifetime of the project. Partners' activities may include but are not limited to engaging with relevant national and local media (print, radio, television, web-based), contributing to SIE's inputs on social media, proactively sharing information with SIE about project results, listing their communication activities in a shared file. Where possible, partners will translate press releases into their national languages and keep SIE informed about plans, by creating lists of national media channels they will try to reach.

11 Timeline

As the AMIGDALA project has different development phases, the D&C focus would be different across each of them:

11.11 Phase 1. Community building

AMIGDALA's first phase (Months 1-12) focuses on building a strong community. By setting up communication channels like a website, social media, and a mailing list, the project will reach targeted stakeholders. Engaging content will be created to explain AMIGDALA's objectives, expected results, impacts, and introduce the consortium members. Through these channels, AMIGDALA will actively engage with the community by responding to inquiries, hosting online events, and encouraging content sharing to build awareness and interest in the project.

11.12 Phase 2. R&D co-creation and diffusion

The second phase (Months 12-48) will be focused on spreading out the main scientific results of the project as they happen through different tools, enabling also the direct external feedback from peers and end users. The cooperation on technical activities with allied projects and initiatives (as P4P) will be executed in this phase.

11.13 Phase 3. Exploitation support

In parallel to the previous phase, this is focused on activities that are oriented to the uptake of the results in support of the project's exploitation strategy. This includes promotion of the software in Open Source (OS) repositories, attending to industry trade fairs, publishing papers summarising the project's results and positive impacts.

12 Actions M1-M6

12.1 Scientific Workshops

The AMIGDALA project hosted two workshops to provide stakeholders with detailed information about the AMIGDALA project, the Community of Practice, its progress, and anticipated outcomes. Both webinars are now available for viewing on a dedicated tab on their website.

The final videos were uploaded to AMIGDALA's YouTube channel, shared on social media and posted on the website: <https://amigdalaproject.eu/webinars/>

Figure 9: AMIGDALA Workshops Section

The first workshop was organised in the framework of how a decision-making framework can analyse industry transformation towards a sustainable EU on April 9, 2024. The workshop was led by several partners from the consortium and provided a platform for in-depth discussions on the project's objectives, methodologies, and anticipated outcomes.

Figure 10: AMIGDALA's banner of its first workshop.

During this first workshop, speakers including Professor Dr-Ing Sebastian Engell from A.SPIRE and Ms. Florie Gonsolin from CEFIC, offered valuable insights into the specific hurdles encountered by the European process industry in aligning with the Green Deal mandates. Engell shed light on the complexities faced by industries, while Gonsolin elucidated key questions and the potential contributions of AMIGDALA towards addressing them.

The workshop not only served as a forum for knowledge exchange but also highlighted the collaborative efforts required to drive sustainable change. Participants engaged in interactive sessions, exploring avenues to shape the project effectively and ensure its relevance in meeting the evolving needs of stakeholders.

The second workshop was held on June 4, 2024, in the framework of how models of demand, trade and industrial production provide useful information for decision-making to make industrial production in Europe climate-neutral and competitive.

During the session, GreenDecision presented its Decision-making framework expertise to develop a dashboard tool that allowed users to seamlessly run complex models.

Dechema showcased its Data Expertise by composing a consistent set of data across the entire modelling scope and creating a library of unit operation and industrial processes for key process industries.

TNO introduced its Integrated Modelling Expertise, detailing the design of the integrated model architecture for linking the models. VITO discussed its Scenario Expertise, focusing on enticing process industries to become carbon neutral, reducing market barriers, and identifying framework conditions and Deloitte presented how members could contribute to the Community of Practice.

Figure 11: Banner of the second workshop

These online sessions served as a platform for stakeholders to showcase the main project ambitions, objectives and methodologies regarding the project's direction and implementation. Key topics discussed included the initial draft of the decision-making framework, expected uses of the project model, and opportunities for collaboration and partnership.

Workshop logistics were carefully coordinated to accommodate the diverse needs and preferences of participants, fostering an inclusive and participatory atmosphere.

Incorporating the registration fields from the webinars into the stakeholder list has been a valuable strategy for enriching the stakeholder database. Through these registration forms, essential information about stakeholders has been captured, including their names, email addresses, locations, industries, organizations, and job titles. This detailed information enables a better understanding of the demographics and interests of stakeholders, allowing for more targeted and personalized engagement strategies.

Additionally, by offering the option to receive updates via the project newsletter, stakeholders are provided with an opportunity to stay informed about project developments while ensuring compliance with EU GDPR regarding data privacy and confidentiality. This proactive approach to stakeholder engagement and data collection has strengthened the communication efforts and enhanced the effectiveness of the stakeholder management plan. The two webinars obtained a total of 83 registrations. In the first webinar, the number of attendees was 34 while in the second webinar was 31 with 44 registrations.

Last but not least, [SIE](#) also contacted [P4Planet](#) in order to promote both webinars amongst their communities.

Figure 12: PROCESSES 4 PLANET publication about the AMIGDALA first webinar.

Figure 13: PROCESSES 4 PLANET LinkedIn Post about the AMIGDALA second webinar.

12.2 Events and Project Website

The AMIGDALA project launched its website in Month 3 (M3), providing a central hub for all project information. Since then, the site has become even more dynamic with regular updates to the "Downloads" and "News" sections.

This includes new content like the recent press release, [the first project newsletter](#), and announcements about partner participation in various events.

The AMIGDALA website attracted a total of 475 users, who collectively browsed the site through 871 sessions (last update June 1, 2024). This translates to an average of 1.83 sessions per user. Overall, there were 1,977 views of the website's content. In terms of geographic distribution, users from the Netherlands topped the list at 85, followed by those from the United States (67), Spain (58), Belgium (53), and Germany (33). The engagement rate was healthy, reaching 59.70% for the audience, this suggests that users are finding the website content interesting and spending time interacting with it.

Figure 14: AMIGDALA's Website Analytics

The AMIGDALA project website is structured on different pages. The most informative and valuable are located in the top menu to make the user find the information and resources at a glance. This menu includes Home, About, Community of Practice, News and Contact. However, in the bottom menu, the legal pages include all the legal, privacy and cookies aspects.

Figure 15: AMIGDALA's Home Page

The AMIGDALA's News Section has been updated with relevant information and events about the project:

- **AMIGDALA Plotting Pathways To Wards Sustainable Industrial Production**, January 30 2024.
- **The AMIGDALA Project Hosts Its Kick-off Meeting In Frankfurt**, February 1, 2024.
- **What Is AMIGDALA? Paving The Way For Europe's Green Future By Analysing Complex Industry Transformation Towards Climate Neutrality**
- **AMIGDALA Holds A Model Workshop In Utrecht** March 26, 2024
- **AMIGDALA Holds Its Inaugural Keynote**, April 6, 2024
- **AMIGDALA Attends The Lux Research Event In Brussels**, April 9 2024
- **The AMIGDALA Project, Member Of The Process4planet Partnership**, May 8 2024
- **AMIGDALA at INDtech 2024**, June 5, 2024.

12.3 Newsletters and press releases

On June 18, 2024, the AMIGDALA initiative published its [first newsletter](#) online. Since multiple stakeholders have contributed, the stakeholder list includes more than 96 contacts.

Figure 16: AMIGDALA's Newsletter

AMIGDALA

The first press release was launched with information of the kickoff meeting. SIE and the consortium partners forwarded the first press release it to approximately 500 trade and local media outlets.

Figure 17: AMIGDALA's First Press Release

Impacts on media outlets and relevant websites

A.SPIRE <https://www.aspire2050.eu/news/new/amigdala-plotting-pathways-towards-sustainable-industrial-production>

Figure 18: AMIGDALA featured in the A.Spire Website

WIT NEWS <https://witnews.eu/amigdala-a-project-to-boost-the-industrial-transformation/>

Figure 19: AMIGDALA featured on the WIT News website

12.4 Social Media

The social media accounts on [Twitter/X](#), [LinkedIn](#) and [YouTube](#) were set up at the beginning of the project and inaugurated with content on the kick-off meeting and the official project press release.

19 Figure 20: X (Twitter) Analytics M1-M6.

20 Figure 21: LinkedIn Analytics M1-M6

Figure 22: YouTube Analytics M1-M6

During this period (M1 – M6), SIE shared **55** publications, achieved **223** followers on both accounts, and our publications reached a total of **20,000** impressions on LinkedIn and X as of June 12, 2024.

12.5 Related initiatives

AMIGDALA acknowledges other initiatives and projects like the [European Climate + Energy Modelling Forum](#), [Energy Modelling Forum](#), [Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium](#), [International Energy Workshop](#), and [Energy Modelling Platform for Europe](#).

A [Related Initiatives](#) section was included on the project's website with the abovementioned three initiatives ([The INITIATE project](#), [Green Steel for Europe](#) and [openENTRANCE](#)). Special attention will be paid to the communication channels of those initiatives.

Figure 23: AMIGDALA's Related Initiatives Tab

12.6 Project Identity

To establish a strong brand identity, AMIGDALA developed a comprehensive visual approach including a logo, brand guidelines (typography, colors, icons, photography style), and communication materials like a detailed brochure, portable roll-up banner, informative poster, project presentation slides, and customizable Word and PowerPoint templates. The materials have been used by partners in physical events such as the INDTech 2024 conference in Namur, Belgium.

Figure 24: AMIGDALA's Roll Up at INDtech 2024

AMIGDALA

The deliverable templates created by SIE in M1 are useful for partners to ensure consistency across deliverables. These templates include information such as title, author, creation date, and use clear headings to structure content. Additionally, they allow for the effective use of tables and figures to present data.

Figure 25: AMIGDALA's PPT Template.

Ensuring accessibility, these materials (a brochure, a roll-up, a logo, a poster, and a project presentation) were made available for download from the project website (<https://amigdalaproject.eu/>) upon launch.

Figure 26: AMIGDALA Website Dissemination Materials

SIE distributed brochures and roll-up banners to project partners who were promoting the project in physical events such as [INDtech event](#) in Belgium (VITO).

12.7 Community of Practice

In the first period of the project, DELOITTE and SIE agreed to create a common space within the AMIGDALA website to explain the [Community of Practice](#). This space is used to explain, engage, and attract the different stakeholders defined as explained in previous sections. In general, this page answers and provides clear explanations such as the ambition of the Community of Practice, the stakeholder categories, the benefits of the community as well as some practical information such as the instructions for being a member, how to stay connected and the Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs).

Figure 27: AMIGDALA's CoP Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)

The [webinars tab](#) of this section provides a wrap-up of the previous activities carried out in the CoP and the possibility of registering for the current activities. Users can view the previous webinars as well as download the presentations of the sessions.

AMIGDALA

Figure 28: AMIGDALA's website, CoP webinars tab

The Community of Practice website section also includes a dedicated space for registration. The registration fields were agreed upon with Deloitte to get the main information necessary to fulfil some of the technical inputs needed for the AMIGDALA project. This registration form offers to the user the possibility to subscribe to the project newsletter as well as information about the EU GDPR.

Figure 29: AMIGDALA's CoP Registration Tab.

Once the user is registered, the user states that agrees with the current GDPR Regulation (EU) and the following information can be used by the AMIGDALA partners only for dissemination or project purposes. Personal or professional information (name, email or any other identifying data) won't be shared outside the AMIGDALA consortium.

AMIGDALA actively promotes the COP by sharing it on their social media channels monthly. Additionally, it will be feature in the newsletters and on the project website.

Figure 30: AMIGDALA's Social Media Post COP

13 Conclusion

This comprehensive Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Plan serves as a strategic roadmap to enhance the reach and influence of AMIGDALA's innovative research and development endeavors. By focusing on essential components such as targeted messaging, strategic channel selection, and a unified visual identity, the D&C Plan guarantees effective interaction with diverse stakeholder groups. Moreover, the plan delineates strong strategies to generate media interest, create compelling project materials, and establish a compelling online presence. This multifaceted approach promotes collaborative knowledge-building and ensures that the project's outcomes resonate with academics, policymakers, industry leaders, and the wider community. The AMIGDALA project will customize its communication efforts and solicit feedback to amplify its overall impact and enrich the P4Planet partnership. Recognizing the significance of effective communication and feedback, AMIGDALA aims to ensure that its research translates into tangible outcomes and aligns with the broader P4Planet objectives for a more sustainable future. The D&C Plan goes beyond mere information dissemination; it sets the stage for continuous engagement and knowledge sharing throughout the lifecycle of the AMIGDALA project, ultimately transforming research into meaningful solutions.

14 Annex: Dissemination Tables

Partner	DATE (MONTH/YEAR)	Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience	How? Communication channel	PLACE	Outcome	Status	Relevant link
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	PRESS RELEASE	SIE PARTICIPATES IN THE AMIGDALA PROJECT	Civil_society	Press_Release	WEBSITE	500	Delivered	https://sustainableinnovations.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/PR-AMIGDALA-2024.pdf
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	KOM	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	8200	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7156581264819421184
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	KOM	Civil_society	Social_Media	TWITTER	1200	Delivered	https://twitter.com/SustainableInnE/status/1750816316502532437
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	KOM	Civil_society	Social_Media	INSTAGRAM	540	Delivered	https://www.instagram.com/p/C2jx1xswsk/?img_index=1
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	PRESS RELEASE ANNOUNCEMENT	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	8200	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7159153180902141952
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	PRESS RELEASE ANNOUNCEMENT	Civil_society	Social_Media	TWITTER	1200	Delivered	https://twitter.com/SustainableInnE/status/1753387839889293427
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	PRESS RELEASE ANNOUNCEMENT	Civil_society	Social_Media	INSTAGRAM	540	Delivered	https://www.instagram.com/p/C22ID6nNmUZ/
SIE	FEBRUARY 2024	WEBSITE POST	PRESS RELEASE ANNOUNCEMENT	Civil_society	Website	WEBSITE	1000	Delivered	https://sustainableinnovations.eu/pr-amigdala-2024-green-deal-project/
DEC	JANUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	KOM	Civil_society	Social_Media	X (Twitter)	185	Delivered	https://x.com/AmigdalaProject/status/1750494455725957282?s=20
DEC	FEBRUARY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	KOM	Civil_society	Social_Media	LinkedIn	1250	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/dechema_ziel-des-projekts-amigdala-ist-die-erforschung-activity-7162807892973191168-4MiB?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
DEC	FEBRUARY 2024	NEWSLETTER	KOM	Civil_society	Newsletter	Newsletter	19300 recipients (opening rate 28%)	Delivered	
DEC	FEBRUARY 2024	PRESS RELEASE	KOM	Civil_society	Press_Release	WEBSITE	686 (website opened)	Delivered	
A.SPIRE	FEBRUARY 2024	AMIGDALA	AMIGDALA. Plotting pathways towards sustainable industrial p	Civil_society	Website	WEBSITE	1000	Delivered	https://www.aspire2050.eu/news/new/amigdala-plotting-pathways-towards-sustainable-industrial-production
ALL	MARCH 2024	2nd Webinar	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Website	WEBSITE	1000	Delivered	https://www.aspire2050.eu/news/new/process-industries-context-european-green-deal
VITO	MARCH 2024	Presentation introducing AMIGDALA	Present AMIGDALA to Joint Research Centre Unit C7 Energy Tr	EU_Institutions	Other	Virtual Presentation	25 attendees	Delivered	
BFI	FEBRUARY 2024	REPOST ON SOCIAL MEDIA	KOM	Civil_society	Social_Media	KOM	521	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:ugcPost:7158106342442897408/?actorCompanyId=101246398
ENEA	MARCH 2024	REPOST ON SOCIAL MEDIA	AMIGDALA COP WORKSHOP	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	132000	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7178359261440139265/?actorCompanyId=101246398
ENEA	MARCH 2024	REPOST ON SOCIAL MEDIA	AMIGDALA 1ST PRESS RELEASE	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	132000	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:ugcPost:7177982014917140481/?actorCompanyId=101246398

AMIGDALA

DEL	apr-24	REPOST ON SOCIAL MEDIA	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	521	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7186776974663532545/?actorCompanyId=101246398
BFI	MAY 2024	REPOST ON SOCIAL MEDIA	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	596	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7190717604318130176/?actorCompanyId=101246398
ENE	MAY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	599	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/in/alessandro-ajdostini-a924489/
ENE	MAY 2024	REPOST ON SOCIAL MEDIA	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	596	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7191752097791406080/?actorCompanyId=101246398
SIT	MAY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	Interview Céline Fellay	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	2000	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7191685919064653825/?actorCompanyId=101246398
DEC	MAY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	286	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:ugcPost:7193869426281041921/?actorCompanyId=101246398
ERS	MAY 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	286	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7191718991985713152/?actorCompanyId=101246398
SIE	JUNE 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	AMIGDALA	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	286	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:720155844418953216/?actorCompanyId=101246398
TNO	JUNE 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	8700	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:share:7199736688288354304/?actorCompanyId=101246398
TNO	JUNE 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	600	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:ugcPost:7199667003060568064/?actorCompanyId=101246398
VITO	JUNE 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	AMIGDALA 2ND WEBINAR	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	500	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:ugcPost:7197152218129514496/?actorCompanyId=101246398
VITO	JUNE 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	INDtech	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	300	Delivered	https://amigdala-project.eu/2024/06/05/amigdala-at-indtech2024-in-namur-belgium/
P4P	JUNE 2024	SOCIAL MEDIA POST	Processes4Planet Partnership	Civil_society	Social_Media	LINKEDIN	600	Delivered	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7201623718739984384/?actorCompanyId=101246398
ALL	JUNE 2024	NEWSLETTER	AMIGDALA's First Newsletter	Civil_society	Newsletter	Newsletter	96	Delivered	https://mailchimp.com/gdpr/153/amigdala-newsletter-1-june-2024

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Partner	Dissemination activity name	What? Type of dissemination activity	Who? Target audience Reached	Why? Description of the objective(s) with reference to a specific project output (max 200 characters)	Status of the dissemination activity	Relevant link	Date
VITO	Presentation introducing AMIGDALA	Meetings	Other	Present AMIGDALA to Joint Research Centre Unit C7 Energy Transition Insights for Policy	Delivered	https://amigdalaapro	MARCH 2024
TNO	LUX RESEARCH: re-tooling of industry for the GreenDeal	Conferences	EU Institutions	Meet potential stakeholders within the EU Green Deal framework	Ongoing	https://amigdalaaproject.eu/2024/04/09/amigdala-lux-research-event-brussels-2024/	apr-24
DEL		Conferences	EU Institutions	Meet potential stakeholders within the EU Green Deal framework	Ongoing		apr-24
VITO	IndTech 2024	Conferences	Industry, business partners	Transformation of European Energy Intensive Industries on the way to climate neutrality	Ongoing	https://amigdalaapro	JUNE 2024
TNO	INCITE Event 2024	Conferences	Industry, business partners	European Innovation Centre for Industrial Transformation and Emissions (INCITE) launch event	Ongoing	https://amigdalaaproject.eu/2024/06/24/amigdala-incite-seville/	JUNE 2024
SIT	Meet our scientists Brightsite	Conferences	Industry, business partners	AMIGDALA was one of the 30 posters presented at the 'Meet our scientists' event, where Brightsite showcased its latest innovations, research, and projects	Ongoing	https://amigdalaapro	JUNE 2024